

The fashion industry has, historically, not placed a great deal of emphasis on the level of comfortability in clothing design. Therefore, many people continue to dress in uncomfortable clothing in order to keep up with the latest fashion trends.

However, studies show that these may be impacting their lives in more ways than they think, as the comfortability of the clothes worn may actually affect cognitive performance. This article will look at this in more detail and provide an overview of what we know so far.

Exam Score

Whilst there is a large body of research into the effect of comfortable clothing on exam scores, perhaps the most definitive and useful data we have has come from Cardello, V. Armando et al in the 2014 study ‘Relationship Between Perceived Clothing Comfort and Exam Performance’.

The study was carried out under naturalistic conditions. It involved asking students who were about to sit an exam to fill out a survey in which they rated the comfortability of their clothing. To account for variance, they also provided information on other variables such as the number of hours they had studied, the type of clothing worn, and their confidence in the exam.

After analyzing the results, the researchers found that there was a significant positive correlation between perceived clothing comfortability and the student’s score in the exam.

Creativity vs Logic

The results of another study in 2015 suggested that comfortable clothing may also have an impact on creativity. In a small study of 60 university students in the US, participants were asked to wear either comfortable clothing or formal attire and then presented with a question which had two correct answers, one of which was straightforward and the other more abstract.

The results of the study found that those who wore formal attire were more likely to select the answer which was straightforward. Those who wore comfortable clothing were more likely to choose the answer which was abstract.

Why?

A number of reasons have been suggested to account for the ways in which comfortable clothing affects our cognitive behavior. For example, the better exam performance may be due to the fact that participants wearing comfortable clothes were less likely to be distracted by the

clothing they were wearing, and thus able to devote more cognitive resources to the exam questions.

However, none of the conclusions drawn or the results of these studies are definitive, and more research is needed in this area to validate these claims. Nonetheless, students who want the best possible chance of performing well in exams may do well to wear comfortable [women's clothing | peaceloveworld.com](http://peaceloveworld.com).